

USING CRITICAL PATH METHODS IN THE MANAGEMENT OF RETROFITTING PROJECTS. CASE STUDY

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Abstract

Purpose – The paper proposes the application of the critical path method in the management of a retrofitting project. The tool used is the Microsoft Project program.

Methodology/approach - It was considered the concrete case of a retrofitting project of a CNC machine tool, a project carried out within a company from Oradea. Thus, the activities to be carried out within the project were identified. Each activity was associated with duration. The necessary resources for carrying out each activity and the costs with them were established. The technological dependencies between the activities were established. All this information was entered into the Microsoft Project program.

Findings – The use of the Microsoft Project program allowed highlighting the critical path within the project. In order to reduce the duration of the project execution, the durations of the activities within the critical path (critical activities) must be reduced.

Research limitations/implications – The paper proposes a retrofitting project management solution.

Practical implications This approach supports the companies whose object of activity is this type of project. The method is a tool to streamline project management.

Originality/value – The paper proposes the use of critical path methods in retrofitting projects, through the Microsoft Project program.

Key words: Retrofitting, critical path methods, Microsoft Project®

Introduction

The management of job production can be assimilated with the management of a project. The project involves the development of activities between which there are technological dependencies, which have a duration and consume resources (Abrudan and Căndea 2002), (Popescu 1996).

A major overhaul of a complex machine can be associated with a project. This is possible from the perspective of the fact that each machine requires the execution of specific operations and requires the use of a different number of different types of resources.

Industrial production involves the use of high-performance machine tools. Obviously, they must be from the CNC category. Purchasing such a car is expensive, especially for small and medium-sized companies. Therefore, they search for a cheaper solution: retrofitting applied to older machine tools. Thus, retrofitting becomes a project that requires proper management.

Machine retrofits are possible in various levels. A retrofit can be as basic as replacing old axes motors and drives with new AC digital servo technology. A comprehensive retrofit for example would include an all new machine electrical system such as CNC control, AC digital servo motors and drives, complete machine wiring, linear and rotary encoders for closed loop positioning feedback, new operator pendent, and new electrical cabinet (EURO Machinery 2019). Retrofitting is the process of replacing the CNC, servo and spindle systems on an otherwise mechanically sound machine tool to extend its useful life. Rebuilding and remanufacturing typically include a CNC retrofit. The anticipated benefits include a lower

cost investment than purchasing a new machine and an improvement in uptime and availability. But there are often other unanticipated benefits to retrofitting including lower energy costs, higher performance and a new level of manufacturing data accessibility (Galco 2019).

The paper proposes the application of critical path methods for the management of the retrofitting project of the machine tool C.B. FERRARI P-46E. The Microsoft Project program is an effective tool for implementing critical path methods (Wolfgang 2007), (Rosca 2011).

The stages of carrying out the retrofitting project of the machine tool at C.B. FERRARI P-46E

C.B.FERRAR produce machines, automated systems and turnkey milling and laser solutions, with 3 and 5 axes, widely used by the world's most advanced manufacturing companies for high-tech machining.

Euroam Industries has initiated a retrofitting process for the C.B. CNC FERRARI P-46E machine tool. This was necessary because: the control panel was outdated and did not work in the parameters, the equipment did not allow the running (simulation) of CAM (Computer Aided Manufacturing) programs, the machine has a high potential in processing complex parts because it has 5 axes. Figure 1 shows the C.B FERRARI P-46E before reconditioning

Figure 1. Machine tool C.B FERRARI P-46E before reconditioning

Carrying out a retrofitting project in the case of a machine tool C.B. FERRARI P-46E involved several stages. A first step was to disconnect the car from the mains. Disassembling the machine is another important step. The solution for disassembling the subassemblies, within the machine and for simple parts, is determined by the design and must take into account the frequency of disassembly required to repair the machine or to replace or recondition a part. Disassembly work depends on the construction of the machine, machine or installation and the type of repair. In the case of the car C.B. FERRARI P-46E the following components have been dismantled: guards and chip tray, electrical installation, spindle motor, actuators.

After disassembly, the parts are washed with oil, detergents or various solutions. The washing process has three phases: washing the parts in the heated solution, the second washing in hot water, drying the parts with compressed air. Brushes are used to wash the parts, and spray pumps to wash hard to reach places. The bearings are washed in benzine or hot mineral oil.

After washing and drying, the parts are sorted into: good parts, reconditioned (repaired) or replaceable parts and unusable parts. Only those that strictly comply with the requirements of the machine documentation will be accepted as good parts. Next, the wear condition of all the component parts is checked and lists are drawn up for the worn parts: electrical components (cables, contactors,

transformers, buttons, etc.), specific parts (axles, gears, bushings, movement screws, etc.), commercial parts (bearings, seals, hoses, balls, springs, screws, nuts, etc.)

The reconditioning method is also influenced by: the functional role of the part, the nature of the material, the heat treatment applied and the hardness of the part, the degree of stress, the service life and the possibility of total or partial restoration of functional characteristics by a certain reconditioning method.

The engineers elaborate the technical documentation necessary for the execution of the specific parts that require reconditioning or their restoration. The simplest parts (spacers, washers, bushings) were made within the company. The parts with a higher degree of complexity were ordered from specialized companies.

The interior surfaces of the castings (speed range housing, electrical panel, servomotor housing and encoder, etc.) are painted. This operation involves the following phases: degreasing, priming, painting.

All these activities are carried out in parallel with the supply of parts, equipment from various suppliers. Figure 2 shows the Fanuc 0I-MF package composed of: spindle motor, servo motors, encoders, control panel, drivers, all electrical part.

Figure 2. Fanuc Equipment (FANUC 2019)

After reconditioning and making the parts, after supplying the necessary ones, we proceeded to the assembly operation. In the case of the retrofitting project of machine tools C.B. FERRARI P-46E, mounting the spindle involved: mounting the drive belt; installation of the main drive motor and the support plate, installation of the main shaft with gears and bearings, installation of the covers.

Figure 3 shows a βi-B series servo motor mounted on the C.B. FERRARI P-46E.βi-B series SERVO is high cost-performance AC servo system. This servo system has enough performance and functions for feed axis and spindle axis of machine tools. And it is also suitable for positioning of industrial machines and peripheral equipment of machine tools (FANUC 2019). Figure 4 shows the electrical panel.

Figure 3. Fanuc βi-B servo motor

Figure 4. Electric panel

The electrical installation and the newly purchased control equipment were installed. Figure 5 shows the control panel of the Fanuc equipment installed on the C.B. FERRARI P-46E. One of the advantages of the new equipment is that it allows editing, simulation and running programs generated with CAM modules (Figure 6). The equipment is also equipped with a dedicated software: FANUC LADDER-III. This is the standard programming system for developing, diagnosing and maintaining sequence programs for CNC PMC ladder, FANUC's integrated PLC. FANUC LADDER-III is a PC software with the following key functions: creating, displaying, editing and printing ladder sequence programs, monitoring and debugging ladder sequence programs, program monitoring, PMC signal status display, PMC signal trace, writing to Flash-ROM, connection to the CNC via Ethernet, works with NCGuide on one or multiple PCs.

Figure 5. Fanuc equipment control panel

Figure 6. Part program simulation

After the assembly of all mechanical, electrical, electronic components and their integration in terms of hardware and software, the machine was put into operation.

The deficiencies revealed were remedied, after which the car was painted. Figure 7 shows the machine tool C.B. FERRARI P-46E after completion of the retrofitting project.

Figure 7a. Machine tool C.B FERRARI P-46E after reconditioning

Figure 7b. Machine tool C.B FERRARI P-46E in tests

Car retrofitting project management C.B. FERRARI P-46E using the critical path method

In the case of the retrofitting project of the car C.B. FERRARI P-46E, the critical path method was applied using the Microsoft Project® program. The use of this program involves the organization of project activities as in Table 1. Thus, the activities to be carried out within the project were identified, these being those presented in the previous paragraph. Each activity was associated with a duration. The

necessary resources for carrying out each activity and the costs with them have been established. The technological dependencies between the activities were established (precedence-succession relations).

Table 1. Retrofitting project activities

Nr. crt.	Activity name	Duration (hours)	Predecessor	Resource Name
1	Disconnect the machine from the mains	1	-	Electrician
2	Disassembly of guards and tray for collecting chips.	5	1	Machinist
3	Removing the electrical installation from the machine	12	2	Electrician
4	Spindle motor removal	3	2	Machinist
5	Disassembly of actuators	5	2	Machinist
6	Disassemble the spindle	4	3,4	Machinist
7	Cleaning of all disassembled components	3	6,2	Machinist
8	Checking the wear condition of all component parts and drawing up lists for worn parts	36	7	Engineer
9	Elaboration of sketches for specific parts that need reconditioning or their restoration	32	8	Engineer
10	Parts executed in collaborations	60	9	Third parties
11	Self-executed parts	30	9	Lathe operator, Milling-machine operator
12	Painting the inner surfaces of the cast parts	12	7,10,11	Painter
13	Supply of all commercial materials	16	8,10	Engineer
14	Purchase of Fanuc 0I-MF package	8	1	Engineer
15	Mount spindle	8	14,13,12,11,10	Machinist
16	Installation of actuators	12	14,13,12,11,10,15	Machinist
17	Installation of electrical installation	24	14,16,15,13	Electrician
18	Commissioning	25	17,16,15,13	Engineer
19	Painting the machine with numerical control	5	18	Painter
20	Functional tests	8	19	Engineer

The allocated resources and labor costs, in lei / hour, are presented in Table 2. The available number from each resource is also specified.

All this information has been entered into the Microsoft Project® program. It allows a complex analysis of all aspects related to the management of a project: defining activities, determining the critical path, allocating resources, analyzing costs, etc. The working hypotheses are: the week was considered to have five working days: Monday, Tuesday, Wednesday, Thursday and Friday; the working day has eight working hours: the program starts at 8⁰⁰ a.m; the break is between 12⁰⁰-13⁰⁰; the end of the working day is at 17⁰⁰. In the paper are presented three of the implementation versions that were analyzed.

Version 1. Considering the information regarding the project activities (Table 1) and those regarding the resources (Table 2), the project was implemented in Microsoft Project obtaining variant 1. The details regarding this version are presented in Figure 8. The program automatically determines the critical path. Critical activities can be highlighted so that they can be more easily accessed and marked in red. Figure 8 shows the Gantt Chart for variant 1. Also, some summary information regarding version 1 of the project implementation in the Microsoft Project program are presented. These are: the project lasts 31.38 days (31 days and 3 hours), the time worked is 334 hours, the costs are 12,617 euros. These costs take into account the cost of Fanuc equipment.

Table 2. Resource available

Nr. crt.	Resursa	Disponibil	Standard (Euro/hour)	Overtime (Euro/hour)
1	Machinist	1	6	10
2	Electrician	1	5	9
3	Engineer	1	7	12
4	Third parties	1	15	30
5	Painter	1	5	9
6	Lathe operator	1	6	10
7	Milling-machine operator	1	6	10

Figure 8. C.B FERRARI P-46E retrofitting project. Version 1

Version 2. In the second variant of project implementation in the Microsoft Project® program (Figure 9) it was considered that between the activities *Checking the wear condition of all component parts and drawing up lists for worn parts* and *Elaboration of sketches for specific parts that need reconditioning or their restoration* to have a precedent-succession *Start-to-Start* relationship with a gap of one day (8 hours). In this case it was found that the duration of the project was reduced to 27.88 days (Figure 9). The overlap, in a certain time interval of the two activities, creates a problem regarding the engineer resource. It is found that there are days when the demand from the engineer resource is higher than available. The shortage of human resources, of a certain category, can be highlighted by the *Resource Graph* option. In Figure 10 it can be seen that the deficit in the *Engineer* resource appears for four days.

Figure 9. C.B FERRARI P-46E retrofitting project. Version 2

Figure 10 Deficit in Engineer resource

Version 3. In order to solve the problem of the deficit regarding the Engineer resource, we looked for the solution of allocating an engineer (Engineer 1) for the activity *Checking the wear condition of all component parts and drawing up lists for worn parts* and another engineer (Engineer 2) for the activity *Elaboration of sketches for specific parts that need reconditioning or their restoration*. Analyzing the result of the project implementation in the Microsoft Project® program, it was found that the longest critical activity is *Parts executed in collaborations* (60 hours). In order to shorten this activity, two

companies were used. Applying the presented changes, resulted the Variant 3 of project implementation presented in Figure 11. In this version the duration of the project is 22.56 days, ie a reduction of 28.10%.

Figure 11. C.B FERRARI P-46E retrofitting project. Version 3

Conclusions

The paper described how the critical path method was used in the management of the retrofitting project of the CNC machine tool C.B. FERRARI P-46E. Thus, the activities corresponding to this project were implemented in the Microsoft Project program considering their durations, the predecessor / successor dependencies between activities, the human resources necessary for the execution of each activity, the costs associated with these resources. The estimated duration and costs were highlighted. The program also provides information on how the allocated resources meet the necessary execution of the project activities. A very important advantage is that the program highlights the critical path and, implicitly, the critical activities. If more resources are allocated for the execution of critical activities, their duration decreases, decreasing the duration of the project execution. Several variants can be analyzed, the decision makers (project manager) can choose the best version.

For the analyzed case, the retrofitting project of the CNC machine tool C.B. FERRARI P-46E, using the critical path method using the Microsoft Project program, three project version were studied. Option 3, by allocating resources more efficiently (additional resources have been allocated for critical activities), allows the project to be completed in 22 days and 4 hours.

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